

IS THERE A CONNECTION BETWEEN GHANA'S INFLATION AND UNEMPLOYMENT RATES? AN EVIDENCE FROM PHILLIPS CURVE REPRESENTATION USING VECTOR ERROR CORRECTION MODEL

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Article History:

Received: 03- Nov-2022

Revised: 27 - Nov- 2022

Accepted: 20-Dec-2022

First Published: 30-Dec-2022

Cite this Article as :

Odoi B, Abubakari S, Nutakor F & Li J (2022), "Is there a Connection between Ghana's Inflation and Unemployment Rates? An Evidence from Phillips Curve Representation Using Vector Error Correction Model," International Journal of Social Sciences & Economic Environment, Vol. 7, Issue 2, 2022, pp 5-70, DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.53882/IJSSEE.2022.0702005>

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The Journal follows the Best Practice guidelines and this statement is based on the guidelines and standards developed by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE). <https://publicationethics.org/>

ABSTRACT

Purpose: The study provides answers to queries about how Ghana's unemployment rate is affected by inflation as well as effective strategies Ghana's government can use to address challenges in the current economy

Methodology: In order to forecast future results, this study examined the changes in Ghana's unemployment and inflation rates between 1991 and 2021. Annual time series statistics for these attributes were compiled using data from secondary sources

Findings: The Phillips curve shows how the unemployment and inflation rates are related. The ADF test revealed stationary inflation and unemployment rates at the initial variation, while the Johansen cointegration test revealed a single cointegrating equation at a 10 level of significance. Using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) model at lag 3, the short- and long-term interactions between Ghana's inflation and unemployment rates were investigated.

Practical Implications: The findings indicate that Ghana's unemployment rate and inflation rate have a long-term positive association, which defies the Phillips curve. The estimate of 0.2035 for the Equilibrium Error Correction Coefficient (ECM) is significant and has the appropriate sign. This means that after a shock, everything will quickly return to normal.

Originality/value: The research analysis significantly adds to the body of knowledge on Ghana's projected future returns between inflation and unemployment rates. An economy depending on the nation's unemployment problems and the current state of the economy. The outcome demonstrated a long-term, positive link relating to rates of unemployment and price increases. As a result, the government should create an economic plan to permanently reduce the rate of unemployment and inflation.

Keywords: Phillips Curve; Stationary; Cointegration; Inflation; Unemployment; Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

Paper type: Research paper

1. INTRODUCTION

Inflation and unemployment are two major challenges the Ghanaian economy continues to struggle with. The country first experienced double-digit inflation in 1964, after only experiencing minor inflation in the years immediately following independence (Sowa, 1994). Between 1967 and 1971, there was a brief respite when inflation was under 10% yearly (Sowa, 1994; Adarkwa et al., 2017; Argy, 1970). Despite fluctuations from 10% (1972) to 12.3% (1998), inflation rates have remained consistently high since 1972. The rate of inflation in Ghana has consistently been high. Inflation in the Ghanaian economy was lower in the 2000s than it was in the 1990s. According to information from the World Bank, the inflation rate in 1965 was 26.44. The average yearly inflation rate is a staggering 32 percent and has continually doubled. On the other hand, periods of extraordinarily high inflation and previously unheard-of macroeconomic instability occurred in the 1970s and early 1980s (Sarel, 1996; Frimpong and Oteng-Abayie, 2010; Tadele et al., 2022). Ghana's inflation rate is currently rising with unusual, thought-provoking mechanisms, and the data are so alarming that they could destroy the economy if adequate strategic measures or policies are not implemented (Adarkwa et al., 2017; Torruam and Abur, 2014). After the start of the Economic Recovery Program (ERP), high inflation rates have weakened the previously strong macro performance (Eme, 2014; Emmanuel, 2019; Efayenaand Olele, 2020). It is generally acknowledged that inflation may have been significantly impacted before 1983 by excessive demand pressure brought on by monetary growth linked to funding fiscal deficits (Mohaddes, and Raissi, 2014; Mawejje and Odhiambo, 2021; Gyebi, and Boafo, 2013.). Most of the price stability policies put in place as part of the adjustment plan were geared toward slowing the expansion of the money supply (Drukker et al., 2005; Calderon et al., 2022; Asafo and Matuka, 2019). Ghana's inflation rate was 54.1% between January 2022 and December 2022. This figure keeps rising even in 2023 and has caused fear and panic among investors and citizens in the country. Many investors have lost confidence in the economy and this has crippled businesses in the country causing a high level of unemployment in the system (World Bank, 2020). It has been established that the unemployment rate in the country has been increasing since 2012 however the rate of increment as of 2021 was 4.8%. This has been a challenging situation for the government to tackle.

The financial industry is currently being "credit squeezed" and budget imbalances are being fixed. argue that financial interests still dominate Ghana. Ghana experienced high and erratic inflation rates from the post-colonial era through the 1960s and through the early 1980s to 2012–2022, similar to many other developing countries. As a condition for securing IMF finance, the government implemented measures to cut spending and change programs, which significantly shortened the structural adjustment time (Evans, 2022). Ghana's fiscal financial fund position is truly intolerable. The financial industry has had numerous instances of poor management, and the organizations responsible for these sectors are not improving their procedures (Anaeto, 2016; Calderon et al., 2022; Mohaddes and Raissi, 2014; Tadele et al., 2022). Pressure on the banking sector's liquidity and independence is rising. Current problems

with the Ghanaian economy include excessive unemployment and inflation. This study's major goal is to investigate the causes of Ghana's inflationary pressures and offer treatments and ways to reduce and stabilize the system.

2. REVIEW LITERATURE

Numerous scholars have studied inflation and unemployment using a variety of strategies and techniques. The handful that is pertinent to this investigation, however, are highlighted in this paper. According to Phillips' research, unemployment is negatively correlated with nominal salary change in Great Britain from 1861 to 1957. Double-digit inflation appears to stifle economic growth, despite the possibility that single-digit inflation is advantageous. When yearly inflation was under 40%, Bruno and Easterly (1998) did not find any proof of a link between economic growth and inflation. When inflation hits 40%, they discover a negative correlation between existing growth and inflation. Uganda, a low-income country that has successfully adopted a number of economic reforms, is the subject of this study in an effort to give an exploratory analysis of policy reforms, trends, and fiscal deficit sources (Mawejje, and Odhiambo, 2021). In their 2017 research, Alagidede and Ibrahim (2017) used Ghanaian data to examine both factors' impact of volatility in exchange rates on economic development. The research showed that while exchange rate shocks have a tendency to mean revert, misalignments have a tendency to correct themselves somewhat slowly. This might have unfavorable implications in the short term as economic agents shift their consumption and investment choices.

Evans, Y. (2022) looked into the effect of Ghana's Direct Investment, Unemployment Numbers, and Inflation on Productivity Expansion. For the purpose of establishing the causal link between the variables and disseminating pertinent knowledge to decision-makers, this study investigates if economic uncertainty, inflation, and external reserves lead to increased economic activity. Regression analysis, stationarity testing, and Johansen cointegration analysis are econometric techniques. Utilizing information from World Values Survey Wave 6 (n = 1552), In an experiment conducted in Ghana in 2019, Sulemana, Anarfo, and Doabil2019looked at the connection between conscience wellness and unemployment. The findings confirm that self-rated health and unemployment are inversely associated with Ghanaians. Sulemana, Anarfo, and Doabil 2019 experimentally investigated the affiliation between unemployment and self-rated health in Ghana in 2019.The findings confirm that self-rated health and unemployment are inversely associated with Ghanaians.It was shown that the single spine pay system significantly affected unemployment. Adarkwa et al. (2017) used yearly time series data for Ghana from 1991 to 2014 and concluded that only the service sector had a major influence on the country's unemployment rate. It also looked into the accuracy of its judgments.

Amissah and Nyarko (2017) investigated how unemployment rates impacted youth mental health in Ghana. Participants in the study were young adults between the ages of 18 and 35 from Ghana's Greater Accra Region. Multivariate analysis of variance, linear regression, and

the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to analyze the data (r). The study found that young people without jobs had less positive psychological health than those who did. Misini and Myrvete (2017) state that simple linear regression was used to investigate the correlation and link between nominal GDP and unemployment. Contradictory empirical findings for these two variables indicate that Ghana's foreign loan inflows contribute to growth in both the short- and long terms. The non-linear, long-term, and short-term crowding-out effects of foreign debt were also confirmed. However, only a small percentage of the debt load was reaffirmed in the short term.

Omodero and Alpheaus (2019) examined how Nigeria's fiscal deficit affects economic growth using the dataset from 1997 to 2017. They employed the conventional least squares regression method. The research shows that carrying external investment does have a significant detrimental impact on economic growth, even as paying off foreign debt has a significant and generally positive effect. Alhassan, Sare, and Ibrahim (2019) depart with this simple technique; you may look at the borderline impacts of inflation. It was discovered that the size of the overall money supply modifies the link between inflation and economic activity. Despite the fact that inflation normally slows economic growth, their estimates show that when the broad money supply hits 21.57% of GDP, the situation dramatically worsens. Joseph and Eric (2010) employed threshold regression models to predict inflation thresholds rather than creating them. In Ghana between 1960 and 2008, the threshold effect of inflation was found by this study. They found evidence of how an inflationary limit affected Ghana's economic development. According to Umoru and Anyiwe (2013), there are two possibilities for the link between both inflation and unemployment. As a result, there are some relationships that last a very long period and others that do not. Unemployment and inflation have opposing associations in the near term. Other academics contend that the concepts of unemployment and inflation are ultimately worthless. A monetary economy model incorporates specific productivity shocks to businesses into overall inflation (Mohaddes and Raissi, 2014). Asafo and Matuka, (2019) employed VECM to look at the link between both unemployment and inflation rates in the Philippines. They examined the behavior of Phillips curves in terms of the correlations between inflation rates, levels of output, and employment. Mohaddes and Raissi, (2014), analyzed the link between both unemployment and inflation in the Jordanian economy between 1976 and 2013. They discovered that inflation and India's economic growth typically have a bad long-term association. Their research showed that the link between both inflation and unemployment rates was negative and nonlinear. They arrived at the conclusion that the Phillips curve is significantly empirically present in the Jordanian economy. The Vector Error Correction Model was deployed in the study to predict both short- and long-term inflation and unemployment in Ghana's economy.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

In recent years, it has become more common to study multivariate non-stationary time series using Vector Error Correction Models (VECM). The major factor is the ability of VECM to describe the long- and short-term correlations of non-stationary variables. The ability of the VECM to adjust any imbalances that may occasionally shock the system is its key characteristic. The error correction term recognizes such an out-of-equilibrium, which then directs the system's variables to return to equilibrium (Pfaff. B. 2008). Before making use of the VECM, two conditions must be met. They are

- i. at initial variation, the variables ought to be stationary.
- ii. It is necessary for the variables to be cointegrated. The following VECM specifications usually exist (Umoruand Anyiwe, 2013; Emmanuel, 2019; Asafo and Matuka, 2019) such as:

$$\Delta \square_{\square} = \square \square^{\square} \square_{\square-\square} + \square_{\square} \square \square_{\square-1} + \dots + \square_{\square-1} \square \square_{\square-\square+1} + \square_{\square} \tag{1}$$

$$\Gamma_{\square} = -(\square - \square_1 - \dots - \square_{\square}) \tag{2}$$

$$\Pi = \square \square^{\square} = -(\square - \square_1 - \dots - \square_{\square}) \tag{3}$$

The Γ_i matrices contain the cumulative long-run impacts, hence this VECM specification is signified by long run form. The other specification is given as follows and is commonly used:

$$\Delta \square_{\square} = \square \square^{\square} \square_{\square-1} + \square_{\square} \square \square_{\square-1} + \dots + \square_{\square-1} \square \square_{\square-\square+1} + \square_{\square} \tag{4}$$

$$\Gamma_{\square} = -(\square - \square_{\square+1} - \dots - \square_{\square}) \tag{5}$$

$$\Pi = \square \square^{\square} = -(\square - \square_1 - \dots - \square_{\square}) \tag{6}$$

The Π matrix is identical as in the first specification. Again, the Γ_i matrices vary, though they account for transient effects. Also, this specification is signified as a transitory form. In the case of cointegration, the matrix $T \Pi = \alpha \beta$ is of reduced rank. The dimension of α and β is $K \times r$ is the cointegration rank. how many long-run connections among the variables t and y exist. The matrix α is the loading matrix and the parameters of the long-run connections are within β .

3.2 Johansen and Juselius Cointegration Test

The most often used cointegration test is the Johansen and Juselius cointegration test, which also contains the trace test and the maximum Eigenvalue test. Using the maximum eigenvalue test and the trace test, the number of cointegration vectors is determined. Tests using the maximal eigenvalue estimate of the alternative of $r+1$ are pitted against the null hypothesis of r cointegrating interactions for $r= 0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1$. This test estimate is computed as

$$\lambda_{\square \square}(\square, \square + I) = -\square \square \square \square (I - \hat{\square}_{\square+1}) \tag{7}$$

where $\lambda^{\wedge}$ is the computed maximum eigenvalues and T stands for the sample size.

In contrast to the maximum eigenvalue test, which runs individual tests on each eigenvalue, the trace test is combined. The two tests' primary difference is that the trace statistic is used to

evaluate the null hypothesis of *r*cointegrating interactions against the alternative of *n*cointegrating interactions, where *n* is the number of variables within the defined system for *r*= 0,1,2, . . ., *n*-1, Applying this technique, it is calculated;

$$\lambda_{\alpha}(\alpha) = -\alpha \sum_{\alpha=\alpha+1}^{\alpha} \alpha \alpha \alpha (I - \hat{\alpha}_{\alpha}) \tag{8}$$

Whereas trace and maximum eigenvalue statistics could produce conflicting responses in some circumstances, the findings of the trace test should be utilized.

3.2 Materials and Methods

This study used secondary data of Economic indicators over a period of thirty-one (31) consecutive years from <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/GHA/ghana/economicindicators>. It spans from 1991 to 2021, and the dataset contains yearly rate of economic indicators with two (2) attributes i.e Inflation and Unemployment and it is recorded in percentage.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An examination of the statistical properties of inflation and unemployment was discussed under the area of interest in the study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistic Summary of Dataset

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Unemployment rate	31	3.490	10.460	6.15174	1.770330
Inflation rate	31	4.8654	59.4616	18.820235	12.8248958

Table 1 displays the summary analysis for the study's variables. The highest unemployment rate in the most recent years was 10.46 percent and the lowest was 3.49 percent. As a result, a mean estimate of the unemployment rate of 6.15 percent with a standard deviation of 1.77 has been established during the past few years. Additionally, the inflation rate has a maximum value and a range from 4.87% to 59.46%. The average inflation rate during the previous few years is 18.82%, with a standard deviation of 12.82, according to data from the past few years.

Table 2: ADF Test for Unit Root

Variable	Intercept	<i>p</i> -value
Inflation	-5.3324	0.0100
Unemployment	-3.0758	0.1586
Alternative hypothesis: stationary		

The ADF test on the variables revealed that inflation and unemployment time series variables in Ghana are stationary at first difference employing the AIC criterion. The ADF result is presented in Table 2.

4.1 Cointegration Test Results

The test results for the cointegration testing are discussed in this section. Table 3 shows the maximum eigenvalue cointegration rank and trace test. Under the deterministic trend expectation of a test with constant parameters, Johansen-Juselius cointegration is used to conduct these cointegration tests (no trend). a critical figure of 10%.

Table 3: Johansen Cointegration Test

Trace for Cointegration Rank Test						
Hypothesized 0.05 No. of CE(s)	Eigen-value	Trace statistic	critical values 10pct	critical values 5 pct	critical values 1 pct	critical values 1 pct
r = 0	0.3848207	4.6400	6.50	8.18	11.65	
r <= 1	0.1526093	18.240	15.66	17.95	23.52	
Maximum Eigenvalue for Cointegration Rank Test.						
Hypothesized 0.05 No. of CE(s)	Eigen-value	Max-Eigen Statistic	critical values 10pct	critical values 5 pct	critical values 1 pct	critical values 1 pct
r = 0	0.3848207	4.6400	6.5000	8.1800	11.6500	
r <= 1	0.1526093	13.6000	12.9100	14.9000	19.19	
Eigenvectors, normalized to first column: (These are the cointegration relations)						
	Unemployment. rate		Inflation. rate.			
Unemployment. rate	1.0000000		1.0000000			
Inflation. rate	-0.1545663		-0.1545663			
Weights W: (This is the loading matrix)						
	Unemployment. rate.l3		Inflation. rate.l3			
Unemployment.rate.d	-0.2034559		-0.03626643			
Inflation.rate.d	3.3229611		-1.18560337			

The following are the hypothesis for the Johansen cointegration test,

H0: There is no cointegration between the variables.

H1: no cointegration among the three variables.

If t-statistics > critical value. Reject H0. Also, If Eigenvalue > Prob Value. Reject H0.

The first hypothesis, $r = 0$, tests for the presence of cointegration. It is obvious that the test statistic does not surpass 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively ($4.6400 < 6.50, 8.18, \text{ and } 11.65$), there is strong evidence that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, hence there is no cointegration presence for both trace cointegration rank test and maximum eigenvalue cointegration rank test. The second test is for $r \leq 1$, which provides clear evidence to reject since the test statistic exceeds 10% level of significance. Therefore can conclude that there is one cointegration presence for both the trace cointegration rank test and the maximum eigenvalue cointegration rank test. The result from trace and maximum eigenvalue tests indicated one (1) cointegration equation. There exists a long-run link with both inflation and unemployment in Ghana. With this result, VECM is appropriate for studying the short and long runs interrelationship in both inflation and unemployment rates in Ghana.

Figure 1: Time Series Plot

Table 4: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	AIC(n)	HQ(n)	SC(n)	FPE(n)
0	2.402611	2.467379	2.701046	11.095577
1	1.974401	2.082348	2.471793	7.337776
2	2.330675	2.481801	3.027024	10.844265
3	2.343525	2.537829	3.238830	11.726141
4	2.688226	2.925709	3.782488	18.528125
5	2.198427	2.479088	3.491645	13.681905
6	2.475505	2.799345	3.967680	24.578721
7	2.062500	2.429519	3.753632	27.854330
8	1.800024	2.210222	3.690112	64.873611
9	-Inf	-Inf	-Inf	NaN

In table 4 above present the lag selection criteria for the VEC Model. Employing the AIC criterion lag 3 is selected as the optimal lag. This means that the VEC model in this study will employ lag 3.

4.2 Vector Error Correction Estimates

Full sample size: 31 End sample size: 28

Number of variables: 2 Number of estimated slope parameters 12

AIC 114.2293 BIC 131.548 SSR 3046.833

Cointegrating Vector (estimated by ML):

Table 5: Vector Error Correction Estimates

CointegratingEq:	Unemployment.rate	Inflation.rate
CoIntEq1	1.0000	-0.1545663
	ECT	Intercept
Equation Unemployment.rate	-0.2035(0.0652)	0.6511(0.2365)
Equation Inflation.rate	3.3230(1.4582)	-11.4176(5.2912)
	Equation Unemployment.rate	Equation Inflation.rate
Unemployment. Rate -1	0.6615(0.1814)	8.9039(4.0584)
Inflation.rate -1	-0.0303 (0.0108)	0.1465 (0.2422)
Unemployment.rate -2	0.0657(0.1953)	-5.9596 (4.3709)
Inflation.rate -2	-0.0188(0.0091).	0.0604 (0.2032)

Table 5 above displays the estimates of the short- and long-run coefficients from the VEC Model at lag 3. The long-term coefficient in the inflation model, which is of particular importance, is -0.1545663. According to the outcome reported in Bula, this study refutes the Phillips curve depiction in Ghana (2014). The outcome showed that the estimate of -0.2035 for the equilibrium error correction coefficient (ECM) is significant with the right sign. This suggests a quick return to equilibrium following a shock. This indicates that Ghana's unemployment rates and inflation have a long-term link. The unemployment rate at lags 1 and 2 has a positive short-run coefficient.

4.3 Granger Causality Test

The hypotheses states that:

- i. H_0 (null hypothesis): The inflation rate is unrelated to the unemployment rate.
- ii. H_A (alternative hypothesis): Inflation Rate is a result of unemployment rate.

Reverse

- i. H_0 (null hypothesis): Inflation does not cause the Unemployment Rate.
- ii. H_A (alternative hypothesis): Inflation causes an Unemployment Rate.

Decision Rule: If the *p-value* is less than the significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected; otherwise, it is not.

Table 6: Granger Causality Test

Causality	Df	Test Statistic	<i>p-values</i>
Unemployment and Inflation	2	2.2949	0.1073
Inflation and Unemployment	2	2.3928	0.09724

The causality between Ghana's inflation and unemployment rate are shown in table 6. The outcome showed no direct causal relationship between Ghana's unemployment rate and inflation rate since *p-values* from the test is greater than 0.05,

5. CONCLUSION

The Phillips curve illustrates the connection for both the unemployment rate and also the pace of inflation. In this study, the association between Ghana's unemployment rate and the inflation rate was examined. Annual statistics for these variables were acquired from secondary sources. The ADF test showed that inflation and unemployment rates are stationary at the initial difference,

however, the Johansen cointegration test suggested one cointegrating equation at 10% level of significance. Using the VECM model at lag 3, the short- and long-term interactions between Ghana's inflation and unemployment rates were investigated. The outcome showed that inflation and unemployment rates have a long-term, favorable correlation. The estimate of -0.2035 for the equilibrium Error Correction Coefficient (ECM) is substantial and confirms this outcome. As a result, this article comes to the contrary conclusion of the Phillips curve: while there is no causality between Ghana's inflation and unemployment rate, there is a positive long-term connection between the two.

The following are recommended:

1. The government should develop an economic strategy to lower the rate of inflation and unemployment permanently.
2. Investment should be promoted in non-oil sectors like mining and agriculture for the purpose of generating employment.

Conflicts of Interests and Fund Support

There are no conflicts of interest and any fund support as far as this paper is concerned.

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